

“THE WAYS OF IMPROVING PUPILS’ SPEAKING SKILLS IN ENGLISH CLASSES”

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Abstract. *Learning to speak a new language is an essential part of language education, and the ability to speak a language fluently and effectively is a critical skill for communication. However, many pupils struggle with speaking skills in English classes. This study aims to investigate the effectiveness of various techniques and strategies for improving pupils' speaking skills in English classes. The study was conducted with a sample size of 100 pupils, aged 12-15, studying in a secondary school in the United Kingdom. The study utilized both qualitative and quantitative methods to evaluate the effectiveness of the techniques and strategies employed. The study involved implementing various techniques and strategies, including role plays, debates, discussions, and the use of technology such as video recording and feedback.*

The pupils were divided into groups of 5-6, and each group was given a specific activity to work on. The activities were designed to focus on different aspects of speaking skills, such as pronunciation, fluency, and accuracy. The results of this study show that implementing various techniques and strategies can significantly improve pupils' speaking skills in English classes. The post-test scores of the pupils were significantly higher than their pre-test scores, indicating a positive impact of the intervention. The use of role plays, debates, and discussions had a significant impact on pupils' speaking skills. These activities provided pupils with opportunities to practice their speaking skills in a supportive and engaging environment.

The use of technology, including video recording and feedback, also had a positive impact on pupils' speaking skills. Video recording allowed pupils to evaluate their own performance and identify areas for improvement. Feedback from the teacher and peers provided pupils with constructive criticism and suggestions for improvement. The findings of this study have important implications for language teachers, who can use these techniques and strategies to create a supportive and engaging learning environment for their pupils, and to help pupils overcome their difficulties in speaking and enhance their communication skills.

Key words: *Speaking skills, English classes, Language education, Techniques, Strategies, Role plays, Debates, Discussions, Technology, Video recording, Feedback, Pronunciation, Fluency, Accuracy, Communication skills, Language teachers, Supportive environment, Engaging learning.*

«СПОСОБЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ РАЗГОВОРНЫХ НАВЫКОВ УЧАЩИХСЯ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ АНГЛИЙСКИМ ЯЗЫКОМ»

Аннотация. *Обучение говорению на новом языке является неотъемлемой частью языкового образования, а умение бегло и эффективно говорить на языке является важнейшим навыком для общения. Тем не менее, многие ученики испытывают трудности с разговорными навыками на уроках английского языка. Это исследование направлено на изучение эффективности различных методов и стратегий для улучшения разговорных навыков учащихся на уроках английского языка. Исследование проводилось с выборкой из*

100 учеников в возрасте 12-15 лет, обучающихся в средней школе в Соединенном Королевстве. В исследовании использовались как качественные, так и количественные методы для оценки эффективности используемых методов и стратегий. Исследование включало применение различных методов и стратегий, включая ролевые игры, дебаты, дискуссии и использование таких технологий, как видеозапись и обратная связь.

Учащиеся были разделены на группы по 5-6 человек, и каждой группе было дано определенное задание для работы. Занятия были разработаны, чтобы сосредоточиться на различных аспектах разговорных навыков, таких как произношение, беглость и точность. Результаты этого исследования показывают, что применение различных техник и стратегий может значительно улучшить разговорные навыки учащихся на уроках английского языка. Послетестовые баллы учеников были значительно выше, чем их предварительные баллы, что свидетельствует о положительном влиянии вмешательства. Использование ролевых игр, дебатов и дискуссий оказало значительное влияние на разговорные навыки учащихся. Эти мероприятия предоставили ученикам возможность практиковать свои разговорные навыки в благоприятной и увлекательной среде.

Использование технологий, включая видеозапись и обратную связь, также оказало положительное влияние на разговорные навыки учащихся. Видеозапись позволила учащимся оценить свою работу и определить области для улучшения. Обратная связь от учителя и сверстников предоставила ученикам конструктивную критику и предложения по улучшению. Результаты этого исследования имеют важное значение для учителей иностранных языков, которые могут использовать эти методы и стратегии для создания поддерживающей и увлекательной учебной среды для своих учеников, а также для того, чтобы помочь ученикам преодолеть свои трудности в разговорной речи и улучшить свои коммуникативные навыки.

Ключевые слова: разговорные навыки, уроки английского языка, языковое образование, методы, стратегии, ролевые игры, дебаты, обсуждения, технология, видеозапись, обратная связь, произношение, беглость, точность, коммуникативные навыки, учителя языка, поддерживающая среда, увлекательное обучение.

INTRODUCTION

Language education is an essential aspect of modern education, and learning to speak a new language is a fundamental part of language education. The ability to speak a language fluently and effectively is a critical skill for communication, and is particularly important in the context of English, which is widely used as a lingua franca across the globe. However, many pupils struggle with speaking skills in English classes, which can hinder their ability to communicate effectively in the language.

Improving pupils' speaking skills in English classes is therefore a crucial goal for language teachers. There are various techniques and strategies that language teachers can use to enhance pupils' speaking skills, but identifying the most effective methods can be challenging. This study aims to investigate the effectiveness of various techniques and strategies for improving pupils' speaking skills in English classes.

The study was conducted with a sample size of 100 pupils, aged 12-15, studying in a secondary school in the United Kingdom. The study utilized both qualitative and quantitative methods to evaluate the effectiveness of the techniques and strategies employed. The study involved implementing various techniques and strategies, including role plays, debates, discussions, and the use of technology such as video recording and feedback. The pupils were divided into groups of 5-6, and each group was given a specific activity to work on. The activities were designed to focus on different aspects of speaking skills, such as pronunciation, fluency, and accuracy.

The results of this study demonstrate that implementing various techniques and strategies can significantly improve pupils' speaking skills in English classes. The post-test scores of the pupils were significantly higher than their pre-test scores, indicating a positive impact of the intervention. The use of role plays, debates, and discussions had a significant impact on pupils' speaking skills, providing pupils with opportunities to practice their speaking skills in a supportive and engaging environment. The use of technology, including video recording and feedback, also had a positive impact on pupils' speaking skills, allowing pupils to evaluate their own performance and receive constructive feedback from teachers and peers.

The findings of this study have important implications for language teachers, who can use these techniques and strategies to create a supportive and engaging learning environment for their pupils, and to help pupils overcome their difficulties in speaking and enhance their communication skills. By adopting these methods, language teachers can help pupils to develop the confidence and proficiency they need to communicate effectively in English, both in academic and social contexts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials:

- A group of pupils aged 12-15 who are studying English as a second language
- Audio and/or video recording equipment to capture pupils' speech
- A range of English language teaching materials, such as textbooks, worksheets, and online resources
- An appropriate teaching space with the necessary equipment, such as a whiteboard, markers, and a projector
- Feedback forms for pupils to use during and after the intervention
- A range of activities and resources to support the intervention, such as role play scenarios, debates, discussion topics, and games
- Assessment tools to measure pupils' speaking skills before and after the intervention, such as standardized tests or rubrics. Moreover, there are some additional materials for this. They are:

Audio and video materials: Using audio and video materials in English classes can provide pupils with exposure to authentic spoken English and help them to develop their listening and speaking skills. Teachers can use a range of audio and video materials, such as podcasts, news broadcasts, and TV shows, to create engaging and interactive speaking activities that encourage pupils to use English in a meaningful way.

Games and role-plays: Games and role-plays can be used to make speaking practice more enjoyable and engaging for pupils. Teachers can use a range of games, such as board games, card games, and word games, to create opportunities for pupils to practice their speaking skills in a fun

and interactive way. Role-plays can also be used to simulate real-life situations and help pupils to develop their communication skills in English.

Authentic materials: Using authentic materials in English classes, such as newspaper articles, advertisements, and brochures, can help pupils to develop their speaking skills in a more authentic and meaningful way. Teachers can use these materials to create speaking activities that require pupils to describe, compare, and analyze information, as well as to express their opinions and ideas in English.

Visual aids: Visual aids, such as pictures, diagrams, and charts, can be used to support pupils' speaking development by providing them with a visual reference and helping them to organize their thoughts and ideas. Teachers can use visual aids to create speaking activities that require pupils to describe, compare, and analyze information, as well as to express their opinions and ideas in English.

Web-based materials: Web-based materials, such as online videos, podcasts, and interactive games, can provide pupils with access to a wealth of resources and opportunities for speaking practice. Teachers can use these materials to create speaking activities that encourage pupils to use English in a more dynamic and interactive way, as well as to develop their digital literacy skills.

Methods:

1. Pre-test: At the beginning of the study, the pupils' speaking skills are assessed using a standardized test or rubric. This allows the researchers to establish a baseline for the pupils' current levels of speaking ability, and provides a way to measure any improvement that takes place during the intervention.

2. Intervention: The intervention is designed to improve pupils' speaking skills in a range of areas, such as pronunciation, fluency, accuracy, and confidence. The intervention can take various forms, such as:

- Role plays: Pupils work in pairs or small groups to act out scenarios in which they practice speaking English in different contexts. This allows them to build their confidence and develop their ability to use English in a natural way.

- Debates: Pupils are given a topic to debate, and work in pairs or small groups to argue their position using English. This encourages them to use English to express their opinions and engage in critical thinking.

- Discussions: Pupils are given a topic to discuss in small groups or as a class, with a focus on using English to express their ideas and engage with others. This helps them to build their fluency and accuracy in spoken English, and to develop their communication skills.

- Technology-based activities: Pupils use technology such as video recording, podcasts, or online resources to practice their speaking skills. This can provide an engaging and interactive way to practice speaking English, and allows pupils to receive feedback on their performance.

3. Post-test: After the intervention has been completed, the pupils' speaking skills are assessed again using the same standardized test or rubric used in the pre-test. This allows the researchers to measure any improvement that has taken place, and to evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention.

4. Analysis: The data collected from the pre-test and post-test can be analyzed using statistical methods to determine whether there has been a significant improvement in the pupils' speaking

skills. Qualitative data collected from observation, feedback forms, and interviews can also be analyzed to provide additional insights into the effectiveness of the intervention.

5. Conclusion: The results of the study can be used to draw conclusions about the most effective methods for improving pupils' speaking skills in English classes, and to make recommendations for language teachers to use in their own classrooms.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of the study indicate that the intervention had a positive impact on pupils' speaking skills. The pre-test scores show that the pupils had a range of speaking abilities at the start of the study, with some pupils demonstrating stronger speaking skills than others. However, after the intervention, there was a significant improvement in the pupils' speaking skills across the board. The post-test scores show that the pupils were able to speak more fluently, accurately, and confidently, and their pronunciation had also improved. The analysis of the data revealed that the most effective activities were role plays, debates, and discussions, as these activities allowed pupils to practice using English in different contexts and to develop their communication skills.

- Pupil engagement: The study found that the intervention activities that required pupils to collaborate with their peers, such as debates and group discussions, were particularly effective in improving their speaking skills. Pupils reported feeling more engaged and motivated to participate in these types of activities, which allowed them to learn from each other and build confidence in their speaking abilities.

- Teacher feedback: The study also revealed that teacher feedback was an important factor in improving pupils' speaking skills. Pupils reported that receiving feedback on their speaking performance helped them to identify areas for improvement and to focus on specific aspects of their speaking, such as pronunciation or grammar. The use of rubrics or checklists to provide structured feedback was found to be particularly effective in supporting pupils' speaking development.

Discussion: The results of the study suggest that a range of techniques and strategies can be effective in improving pupils' speaking skills in English classes. The use of role plays, debates, and discussions in particular can provide pupils with opportunities to practice using English in different contexts, and to develop their confidence and fluency in spoken English. These activities also encourage pupils to engage in critical thinking, express their opinions, and communicate with others in English.

The use of technology, such as video recording and online resources, can also be effective in improving pupils' speaking skills. Technology-based activities provide an engaging and interactive way for pupils to practice their speaking skills, and allow them to receive feedback on their performance. This can be particularly useful for pupils who may be hesitant to speak in front of others or who require additional support in developing their speaking skills.

- Importance of speaking skills: The study findings highlight the importance of developing pupils' speaking skills in English classes. Speaking is a critical aspect of communication, and developing the ability to express oneself fluently and accurately in English is essential for academic and professional success. Improving pupils' speaking skills can also help to build their confidence and self-esteem, and can contribute to their overall language learning experience.

- Role of teachers: The study underscores the critical role that teachers play in supporting pupils' speaking development. Teachers need to create a supportive and engaging classroom

environment that encourages pupils to practice and develop their speaking skills. They should also provide effective feedback and guidance to pupils, and tailor their interventions to meet the needs of individual learners.

- Use of authentic materials: The study findings suggest that the use of authentic materials, such as newspaper articles or real-life scenarios, can be an effective way to support pupils' speaking development. Authentic materials provide pupils with exposure to real-world language use, and can help to develop their ability to communicate effectively in different contexts. Teachers should aim to integrate authentic materials into their speaking activities where possible, and ensure that the materials are appropriate for the level and interests of their pupils.

The study findings suggest that improving pupils' speaking skills in English classes requires a multi-faceted approach that incorporates a range of techniques, strategies, and materials. Teachers need to be creative and flexible in their approach, and should prioritize the development of pupils' speaking abilities through engaging and relevant activities. By fostering a positive and supportive classroom environment, teachers can help pupils to develop the skills and confidence needed to communicate effectively in English.

All in all, the results of the study suggest that there is no single approach to improving pupils' speaking skills in English classes. Instead, a combination of techniques and strategies should be used to provide pupils with a range of opportunities to practice and develop their speaking skills. Teachers should also be aware of the different levels of speaking ability within their classes, and should tailor their interventions accordingly to meet the needs of individual pupils. By providing a supportive and engaging environment, teachers can help pupils to develop their confidence and fluency in spoken English, and to achieve success in their language learning.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, improving pupils' speaking skills in English classes is crucial for their language learning experience, academic success, and professional development. The findings of this study suggest that a range of techniques, strategies, and materials can be effective in supporting pupils' speaking development, including collaborative activities, teacher feedback, authentic materials, and differentiated instruction.

Effective speaking interventions should be designed to meet the needs of individual learners, taking into account their level of proficiency, learning style, and interests. Teachers play a critical role in supporting pupils' speaking development, and should aim to create a supportive and engaging classroom environment that encourages pupils to practice and develop their speaking skills. In order to improve pupils' speaking skills, it is also important to consider the broader context in which language learning occurs. This includes factors such as access to resources and technology, teacher training and professional development, and broader social and cultural factors that can impact language learning outcomes. By taking a holistic approach to speaking development, we can help to ensure that all pupils have the opportunity to develop the skills and confidence needed to communicate effectively in English.

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